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Analysis Good Governance of Corruption Eradication toward Penta Helix Model in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Transparency International released an annual report on the corruption perception index in 2018. The survey results of 180 countries showed a bad score because more than two-thirds scored less than 50. The highest score is 100, which means very clean or free of corruption, and the lowest is zero which means it is very corrupt. Indonesia must learn from New Zealand and Australia who have succeeded in helping improve the corruption perception index in their country, even though Indonesia's corruption perception index experienced an upward trend in 2014-2018. In an effort to analyze Good Governance in eradicating corruption in Indonesia, the researchers applied the Penta Helix Model, better known as the ABCGM concept, namely Academicians, Business, Community, Government, and Media to reduce the level of corruption in Indonesia. This research method is qualitative to investigate, find, describe, and explain the quality or features of social influences that cannot be explained, measured or described through a quantitative approach. The Penta Helix model is considered to have a positive influence in eradicating corruption.

Keywords: Good Governance, Corruption, Penta Helix Model

Introduction

The International gatherings such as the International Anti-Corruption Conference series (IACC) and the Global forum series have been playing a pivotal role in setting the agenda of many countries to combat corruption acts in the world. Two global gatherings of anticorruption practitioners from country governments, international organizations, donor countries, international non-governmental organizations, and national political leaders have gained in stature and reach.

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The most challenging governance problem afflicting many countries nowadays is a corruption. It is as one of the factors for financial crisis at economic level in East Asian especially in Indonesia, the Republic of Korea, and Thailand. The interlocking relationship of business and government were previously viewed as part of the way of doing business and practicing politics—a useful partnership crucial to strategic policymaking.

While At the political level, corruption has become the national agenda in political development because of its role, at one point the heads of government themselves of Indonesia, the Philippines, and Thailand were in the dock on corruption-related charges. Peaceful populist protest forced the Philippine president, Joseph Estrada, to step down in January 2001. In July 2001 Indonesia's parliament removed President Abdurrahman Wahid from office partly because of corruption allegations. Thaksin Shinawatra, prime minister of Thailand, was indicted by the National Counter-Corruption Commission. Other high-level political leaders have also been convicted recently on corruption-related charges in China, Indonesia, the Philippines, and Thailand.

International Transparency as a world body observing efforts to eradicate corruption by the government, business and civil society released the annual report of the Corruption Perception Index in 2018. The results of a survey of 180 countries showed a bad picture because more than two-thirds scored less than 50. The highest score is 100, which means very clean or free of corruption, and the lowest is zero which means very corrupt. Indonesian President's spokesman Johan Budi acknowledged this was not a leap but clearly showed improvement, especially in public services. If at the beginning of Jokowi's government in 2014 our GPA was 34, now it is 38. Although it is not a very big jump, it shows a process of improvement, especially in public services because this index measures the extent to which government performance is improved in the countries surveyed by Transparency International.

Figure 1. 2018 GPA for the Asia-Pacific Region
Source: (Courtesy: Transparency International)

The Indonesian Anti-Corruption Behavior Index (IPAK) in 2018 is lower than the previous year. Data from BPS-Statistics Indonesia shows that this year's IPAK is at the level of 3.66 on a

scale of 0-5, the previous year at 3.71. The higher the index indicates the higher the anti-corruption behavior of the people. Conversely, the lower the index, the lower the anti-corruption behavior. Corruption behavior index from the dimension of public perception this year rose to 3.86 from the previous year. While the experience dimension decreased to 3.57 from 3.6. Based on data from the Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK), from 2004 to the end of May 2018 there were 856 state and private officials entangled in corruption cases. Of these, as many as 205 people are members of the House of Representatives (DPR).

Figure 2. Anti-Corruption Behavior Index
BPS-Statistics Indonesia

The development of criminal acts of corruption in Indonesia, both in terms of quantity and quality today can be said that corruption is no longer an ordinary crime, but it is already an extraordinary crime due to its complexity and negative effects. For this reason, eradicating efforts is needed in extraordinary ways. Recognizing corruption as a transnational crime, the Government of Indonesia is committed to eradicating corruption together with countries in the world, as evidenced by ratifying the United Nations Convention Against Corruption (UNCAC 2003) through Law No. 7 of 2006. As a ratifying country, Indonesia is required to implement the UNCAC provisions in full. It's just that in implementing the provisions of UNCAC, violation of regulations related to the prevention and eradication of corruption as stipulated in the UNCAC is still not optimal. The results of the gap analysis conducted by the KPK indicate that, a number of UNCAC provisions have not been fully adopted by Indonesia.

The obligation to eradicate corruption, not only rests with law enforcement officials, is not the responsibility of government officials, but the obligation to eradicate corruption is also the responsibility of the Indonesian people as a whole. For this reason, efforts to prevent and eradicate corruption require the participation of all components of the nation, because this is not only a matter of law enforcement, but also of ways of thinking and behavior. In other words, corruption is also a social and cultural problem. So based on the background above this study will analyze the role of all elements in combating corruption in Indonesia based on the principle of good governance in the perspective of penta helix.

This study uses a qualitative descriptive approach. Descriptive research is research on problems in the form of the current facts of a population that includes the assessment of attitudes or opinions of individuals from a population that includes the assessment of attitudes or opinions on individuals, organizations, circumstances, or procedures. This research can relate to a particular case or a fairly large population. According to Lexy J. Moleong (2005: 6), qualitative research methods are research that intends to understand the phenomena experienced by research subjects. For example, behavior, perception, motivation, action, etc., holistically, and by way of description in the form of words and language, in a special natural context and by utilizing various natural methods.

Good governance has 8 major characteristics. It is participatory, consensus oriented, accountable, transparent, responsive, effective and efficient, equitable and inclusive and follows the rule of law. It assures that corruption is minimized, the views of minorities are taken into account and that the voices of the most vulnerable in society are heard in decision-making. It is also responsive to the present and future needs of society. In terms of functional aspects: governance can be seen from whether the government has been functioning effectively and efficiently in an effort to achieve the goals set, or the like? UNDP defines it as "*the exercise of politics to manage a nation's affair at all levels*". So that governance has three elements, namely:

- a. Economic Governance, including the decision-making process that facilitates domestic economic activities and interactions between economic providers. Economic governance has implications for equity, poverty, and quality of life.
- b. Political Governance, are the processes of making decisions for policy formulation.
- c. Administrative Governance is the process of implementing a policy system. Therefore, institutions of governance include 3 domains, namely: State (state or government), private sector (business sector or business world) and society (society) which interact with each other and carry out their respective functions.

The characteristics of good governance are:

- a. *Participation*
Every citizen has a voice in making decisions. Participation is built on the basis of freedom of association and speaking and participating constructively.
- b. *Rule of law*
The legal framework must be fair and be implemented indiscriminately, especially the law for human rights.
- c. *Transparency*
Transparency is built on the basis of freedom of information flow. Processes, institutions and information are directly acceptable to those in need. Information can be understood and can be monitored.
- d. *Responsiveness*
Institutions and processes must try to serve stake holders.
- e. *Consensus Orientation*
Good Governance mediates different interests to obtain the best choice for broader interests in terms of policies and procedures.
- f. *Equity*
All citizens have the opportunity to improve or maintain their welfare.

g. *Effectiveness and Efficiency*

The processes and institutions produce according to what has been outlined using the best available resources.

h. *Accountability*

Decision makers in government, the private sector and the community are accountable to the public and stakeholder institutions. This accountability depends on the organization and the nature of the decision made, whether the decision is in the international or external interest of the organization.

i. *Strategic Vision*

Leaders and the public must have a broad and far-reaching perspective of good governance and human development in line with what is needed for such development.

Based on this understanding of governance, there are three domains of governance institutions that interact with each other, namely the State or government; the business world (private sector) and society (society). These three institutions must be interconnected and work with the principles of equality, without any effort to dominate one party to another. In fact efforts to realize governance have also been carried out, among others manifested in MPR Decree Number XI / MPR / 1999 concerning State Administration that is clean and free of corruption, collusion and nepotism and in Law Number 28/1999 concerning Clean State Administration and Free from KKN, as stated in Article 3, the principles of state administration include: the principle of legal certainty; the principle of orderly administration of the state; the principle of public interest; the principle of openness; principle of proportionality; the principle of professionalism; and the principle of accountability. Both of these regulations are the first steps in reform in the area of good governance

The Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK) was formed based on Law Number 30 of 2002 concerning the Corruption Eradication Commission, the Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK) was given the mandate to eradicate corruption in a professional, intensive, and sustainable manner. KPK is an independent state institution, which in carrying out its duties and authorities is free from any power. The KPK leadership in charge of four fields, consisting of the fields of Prevention, Enforcement, Information and Data, as well as Internal Oversight and Public Complaints.

In carrying out its duties, the KPK is guided by five principles, namely: legal certainty, openness, accountability, public interest, and proportionality. The KPK is responsible to the public and submits its reports openly and periodically to the President, Parliament and BPK. The KPK is led by a KPK Chairperson consisting of five people, a chairman and member and four deputy chairmen and members. The five KPK leaders are state officials, who come from government and community elements. KPK leaders hold positions for four years and can be re-elected only for one term. In making decisions, KPK leaders are collegially collective.

Penta Helix model is better known by the ABCGM concept of Academics, Business, Community, Government, and Media (Slamet et al, 2017). The main key to the success of this innovation is the existence of synergy and strong commitment among stakeholders in carrying out. The Penta Helix model is very useful to be managed based on actors. Here is a picture of the Penta Helix model:

Figure 3. Penta helix model

Source: Slamet, et al 2017

Result and Discussion

Academic

Recently there has been a wave of demonstrations in various regions of Indonesia. A wave of student demonstrations took place in a number of regions. The action took to the streets voiced one mission which was to reject the Revision of the KPK Law and the Draft Criminal Code which was considered as a setback for democracy. The revision of the KPK Law and the Penal Code draft have caused a turmoil of rejection in society because a number of revisions are loaded with problematic articles because they threaten democratic freedom. The controversial article to weaken the KPK is as follows: Independence of the KPK is threatened, Tapping is difficult and restricted, Establishment of a Supervisory Board elected by the DPR, sources of investigators and investigators are limited, Prosecution of corruption must coordinate with the Attorney General's Office, cases that receive public attention are no longer a criterion, The authority to take over cases in the prosecution was cut, the strategic powers in the prosecution process were eliminated, the KPK had the authority to stop investigations and prosecutions, and the authority of the KPK to manage LHKPN reporting and inspection was cut.

UAI Lecturer in Law Faculty Agus Surono said that students' struggles must be consistent in guarding the process of eradicating corruption. According to him the role of the academic community and the community is contained in the Corruption Eradication Act. The role of academics in society can be manifested by building anti-corruption networks, anti-corruption communities, anti-corruption seminars, establishing honesty canteens and in certain moments academics appearing to provide insight into developing issues of corruption. All of that can be done by academics both as a driving force that directs an activity and as a main actor.

In the Public Lecture of Yogyakarta Muhammadiyah University new students Slamet assessed that the eradication of corruption can now be done through good preventive efforts by building a control system and improving public services. In addition, according to him the improvement of

the process of procurement of goods and services becomes important in efforts to eradicate the crime. Besides that, continued Slamet, repressive efforts are needed to give a deterrent effect to corruptors and no less important is to provide anti-corruption education to the public.

Within the campus scope students must prove two things: They are giving examples that are able to be the internal organizational organizers of a campus that is clean of corruption. Guiding campus policies on academic and non-academic activities on campus. With the strength possessed by students in the form of enthusiasm in voicing and fighting for the values of truth and courage in opposing all forms of injustice. Students occupy an important position in efforts to eradicate corruption in Indonesia. The power is like a double-edged knife, on the one hand, students are able to encourage and move the community to act on system injustice including acts of office abuse and corruption. While on the other hand, students are a pressing factor for law enforcement for corruptors and guards for creating public policies that are in favor of the interests of the public at large.

Business/Private Sector

The role of the private sector is very important in preventing corruption. How does a corporation build good corporate governance and corporate liability in preventing corruption? Abraham explained, the private sector, State-Owned Enterprises (SOE) and Civil Society Organizations (CSO), must apply the principles of good corporate governance. In applying this principle, Abraham mentioned three crucial things. First is the responsibility of superiors not to order subordinates to commit acts of corruption. Second, the responsibility of superiors to not let subordinates commit corruption, and thirdly how companies build corruption prevention systems by implementing internal control programs, making rules and codes of ethics.

By implementing these three things, a clean, transparent and accountable business environment will be created. If these three crucial things are not considered by the private sector and bribery practices continue to occur, there will be unfair competition practices and have an impact on the economic aspects of a nation. He added, so far bribes from the private sector to state administrators and civil servants have occurred due to the absence of regulations regarding facilitation payments. Only the state administrators and public servants have rules about prohibiting the receipt of gifts or promises as stated in Law 31/1999 on Eradicating Corruption. Bribery and gratification are offenses that arise on the principle of supply and demand. Entrepreneurs want their affairs smooth and fast. While on the other hand, civil servants or state administrators are still constrained by low income and lack of integrity.

According to the Program Coordinator of the Directorate of Education and Community Services Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK), Roro Wide Sulistyowati, based on data from 2014-2017, the most corrupt perpetrators are private professions, 164 cases. While the second rank is 148 cases and the third rank are DPR / DPRD members. Furthermore, the mayor, regent and deputy regent rank next with 60 cases, followed by 25 service heads, governor 17 cases, governor 17 cases, 15 judges, commissioner 7 cases, ambassadors 4 cases and others 81 cases.

Thus, if the private sector can participate and be involved in creating a healthy business climate by not doing dirty or corrupt practices or practices while doing business, it will restrain corrupt practices from one side - the private sector - so that it can suppress corrupt practices between the government and private. If we look at companies in the United States, there are already many companies that have a special section that ensures that their business runs according to the law and can prevent corruption in that company. The United States government also allows companies to crack down on employees involved in corruption. In return, companies that are considered successful in preventing and detecting corruption will receive incentives from the local government.

Community

Law of Republic Indonesia Number 31 of 1999 concerning Eradication of Corruption in Article 41 paragraph (5) and Article 42 paragraph (5) confirms that the procedures for implementing public participation and giving awards in the prevention and eradication of criminal acts of corruption need to be regulated by Government Regulation. The role of the community is intended to realize the rights and responsibilities of the community in running a state that is clean from corruption.

In efforts to prevent and eradicate corruption, the public has the rights and responsibilities in the sense that the community participates in efforts to prevent and eradicate corruption. Community participation in prevention and eradication efforts is manifested in forms such as, seeking, obtaining, providing data, or information on corruption and the right to submit suggestions and opinions and take responsibility for the prevention and eradication of corruption.

The role of the community is intended to realize the rights and responsibilities of the community in the administration of a State that is free and free from corruption. In addition, with this participation the community will be more passionate to carry out social control over criminal acts of corruption. In the Republic of Indonesia Government Regulation Number 71 of 2000 Concerning Procedure for the Implementation of Community Participation and the Awarding of Prevention and Eradication of Corruption, is regulated and mentioned in Chapter III of the regulation, which can be elaborated in detail as follows:

- a. Article 7 paragraph (1): every person, community organization or non-governmental organization that has contributed in an effort to help prevent or eradicate corruption has the right to receive an award. Paragraph (2) states: the award referred to in paragraph (1) may be in the form of a charter or premium.
- b. Article 8: provisions regarding the procedure for awarding and the form and type of charter as referred to in article 7 paragraph (2) shall be determined by a decision of the Minister of law and legislation.

Article 8 paragraph (1) of Law No.28 of 1999 concerning State Administration that is clean and free of Corruption, Collusion and Nepotism: The role of the community in the administration of the state is the right and responsibility of the community to participate in realizing a clean State Operator Paragraph (2): The relationship between State Administrators and the public is carried

out by adhering to the general principles of state administration as referred to in Article 3 of Law No.28 of 1999, namely: The Principle of Legal Certainty; Principle of Public Interest; Principle of Openness; Principle of Proportionality; Principle of Professionalism; and Accountability Principle

Explanation:

Strengthening community participation is carried out among others by:

- a. Increase transparency and public contribution in decision making
- b. Ensuring that the public has access to information effectively
- c. Implementation of community information services that contribute to anti-corruption attitudes as well as community education programs including school and university curricula
- d. Respect, promote and protect the freedom of seeking, receiving, announcing and disseminating information related to corruption. Freedom is intended in accordance with statutory restrictions (related to the rights and good name of others and for the sake of protecting national security / public order, health or morality of the community).

Governments

The Government of Indonesia seeks to eradicate corruption that has targeted small communities so that the Indonesian state does not experience deterioration in various aspects and fields due to the impact of this corruption itself. Efforts made by the government in eradicating corruption consist of prevention efforts, enforcement measures, and educational efforts.

a. Prevention Measures

These preventive actions are intended so that the community has a strong fortress to avoid acts that reflect acts of corruption in their daily lives. Efforts to prevent corruption are carried out by the government based on the basic values of Pancasila so that the prevention measures are not in conflict with the values of Pancasila itself.

Other preventive actions that are quite strategic in the context of preventing the occurrence of criminal acts of corruption in Indonesia include: Increasing the effectiveness of policies and institutions, especially related to public services, including among others the Population Number (NIK) policy integrated in the Single Identification Number (SIN) program; Improve supervision of government services, so that they can be accessed by a transparent and accountable public; Improve regional financial management including management of government goods / services procurement; Strengthening anti-corruption commitments, (including through educational institutions in education) related to national integrity for community members, business people and government / state apparatus; Bureaucratic Reform is an effort to make fundamental reforms and changes to the system of governance, especially concerning the institutional aspects, management and human resources of the apparatus; and Implement WASKAT effectively for every leader at all levels / work units and provide good role models and obey all existing legal regulations.

b. Enforcement Measures

Enforcement efforts carried out by the Indonesian government against perpetrators of criminal acts of corruption. In the implementation of efforts to counter corruption, the government is assisted

by an independent institution to eradicate corruption, namely the Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK). Actions carried out by the Corruption Eradication Commission since the Corruption Eradication Commission established in 2002 have produced results that can be referred to as maximizing results. Enforcement efforts carried out by the KPK against corruption is an effort that is not kidding and indiscriminately.

Anyone who is indicated to have committed a criminal act of corruption will be prosecuted by this independent institution without exception. In carrying out its duties, the Corruption Eradication Commission needs the role of judicial institutions in upholding justice in Indonesia, especially those relating to corruption. Of course, the implementation of the judicial process is carried out in accordance with the mechanism of the justice system in Indonesia and based on applicable laws and laws. Actions taken by the government through the KPK against perpetrators of corruption are intended to have a deterrent effect on the perpetrators and indirectly provide shock therapy to those who intend to commit criminal acts of corruption both within the government and in everyday life.

c. Educational Efforts

Educational efforts undertaken by the government in its efforts to eradicate corruption are efforts made through the education process. The education process in Indonesia is carried out in three types namely formal, informal, and non-formal education. Through the education process, the public is given anti-corruption education from an early age so that the public is well aware of the dangers of corruption for countries, especially Indonesia.

In addition, through education provided by the government, the role of students in eradicating corruption can also be maximized so that these students can provide good examples for their younger siblings and for the general public on how to eradicate corruption from within themselves. Educational efforts carried out by the government are also included as an effort to build the nation's character in the era of globalization to eradicate the growth of a culture of corruption that can harm the life of society and the state

The preventive measures taken by the government in the context of efforts to eradicate corruption in the territory of Indonesia include:

a. Cultivating the National Spirit

Positive inculcation of the national spirit was carried out by the Indonesian government in the form of counseling or general discussion of the values of Pancasila as the personality of the Indonesian nation. Personality based on Pancasila is a personality that upholds the national spirit in the application of Pancasila in everyday life. With the instilling of the national spirit of Pancasila in the community, public awareness of the impact of corruption on the state and society will increase. This will encourage the people of Indonesia to avoid various forms of corruption in daily life for the survival of the nation and country.

b. Doing Honest and Open Employee Acceptance

Prevention efforts as a form of corruption eradication efforts carried out by the government can be done through honest and open reception of state apparatus. Honesty and openness in the

recruitment of employees conducted by the government shows the government's serious efforts to eradicate criminal acts of corruption related to bribery in hiring employees. The government that has tried to take preventative measures in recruiting employees needs to be welcomed by the community, especially in supporting the government's efforts.

c. Appeal to the community

Appeals to the community are also carried out by the government in an effort to prevent it as a form of efforts to eradicate corruption in the community. The appeal is usually made by the government through extension activities in the sphere of small communities and emphasizing the latent danger of corruption in the Indonesian state. In addition, the appeal made by the government to the community emphasizes what can trigger corruption in the community to the government elite.

d. Community Welfare Management

Government efforts to eradicate corruption are also carried out through prevention efforts in the form of community welfare exploitation by the government. The government is in the form of the welfare of the community through the provision of public facilities and the establishment of policies governing the welfare of the people. The welfare of the people pursued by the government is not only physical welfare but also physically and spiritually. The hope, through efforts to improve community welfare can improve the welfare of life can provide reinforcement to the community to minimize the occurrence of acts of corruption in the community so that it can create a civil society that is clean from corruption in daily life.

e. Recording of Assets

The repainting of assets is carried out by the government in order to monitor the circulation of assets owned by the community. In 2017, the government sets a policy to the community to report their assets as a form of efforts to prevent corruption that can occur in the community. The recording of assets owned by the community is not only in the form of cash assets held in banks, but also against other ownership assets in the form of goods or land. In addition, the government also investigates the origin of assets owned by the community to find out whether the assets owned by the community indicate corruption or not.

Media

A media is one of the pillars that are the mainstay in eradicating corruption. Therefore, members of the press must consistently fight corruption crimes in Indonesia. Corruption that grows systemically by hiding behind the law makes the presence of the press threatened and it is difficult to reveal cases of corruption that occur in government institutions. "Many legislative products threaten press freedom. Like the Bill on State Secrets. It's the same as the corruption protection bill," said Sinar Harapan Daily Editor in Chief Kristanto Hartadi, one of the speakers in the discussion.

The significant role of the press in the disclosure and handling of corruption cases in Indonesia shows how important the role of coolie inkers is. Corruption is considered systemic by hiding behind the law, making the presence of the press increasingly threatened in revealing corruption cases in government agencies. As stated by one of the speakers, Kristanto Hartadi, who is also the Chief Editor of Sinar Harapan. Many legislative products threaten press freedom. Like the Bill on State Secrets. It's the same as the Corruption Protection Bill. Meanwhile, one member of the Century Maruarar Sirait Special Committee (FPDI-P) expressed his gratitude to the media crew who had become pillars of democracy.

By presenting actual news from various issues relating to corrupt practices, law, politics and so on, it shows that the media actually has an essential contribution in supporting the process of democratic development. Moreover, we are currently in a period of democratic transition which is one of the ways through governance reform. Therefore, this is the right time for the mass media to support the process of reforming good governance through informative, intelligent, critical and responsible news. In the current context, the role of the mass media is demanded to be able to objectively pick up various corruption news at various levels of government. Moreover, President Susilo Bambang Yudhoyono in the Asia Pacific Economic Cooperation Forum (APEC) stated that currently corruption is Indonesia's biggest enemy besides terrorism. So, actually there is no reason for the media not to support the eradication of corruption in the country through the disclosure and coverage of corruption cases.

For example for covering corruption cases, the role of the media is very relevant to what is stated in the Press Law 40/1999. Article 6 of this law states that the media must be able to carry out the functions of controlling behavior, criticizing, correcting, and advising on matters of public concern. So, in accordance with the mandate of the Press Law, corruption and various other forms of irregularities should be targeted by the mass media. On the other hand, the media are also required to provide accurate, independent and critical reporting. These three elements of reporting are in accordance with the principle of transparency which is one of the concepts of good governance. So if these three things are fulfilled, then there is no doubt that the media is making a significant contribution towards the reform of good governance.

But unfortunately, there are still many media that are not yet completely independent and objective from certain interests (example: the owner). Many reports in the media are not objective and only benefit a handful of groups. So the news he presented was no longer clear. Often the media are actually used as a justification for a particular case. This is what can lead to misunderstanding in the reading community. Because readers are consumers who enjoy the results of the media industry production directly. As for the media, not only can they act as providers of information, but on the contrary the media can also do things that are provocative and influence the opinions of their readers. If this happens, it will become a stumbling block to the democratic process.

Conclusions and Suggestions

Conclusions

This study concluded that the eradication of corruption in Indonesia can be carried out effectively and efficiently from prevention efforts, enforcement measures if collaborative action can be applied between elements of good governance (participatory, consensus oriented, accountable, transparent, responsive, effective and efficient, equitable and inclusive and follows the rule of law) and elements of penta helix (academics, business (private sector), community, government and media). The Synergy will support the KPK as a "Super Body" in eradicating corruption in running its main task in the field of Prevention, Enforcement, Information and Data, and Internal Control and Public Complaints. Without those collaborations the eradication of corruption in Indonesia will be very difficult to fight.

Suggestions

Increasing greater public awareness of the National Strategy to Eradicate Corruption through public campaigns;

Strengthening the KPK law as against the Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK) in its capacity to implement the National Strategy;

Greater transparency and trust in sharing national information on anti-corruption efforts.

Public Control by Academicians including Anti-Corruption Education and pressure from Students

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